

Spectrophotometric Quantification Of Vericiguat By 3-Methyl-2-Benzothiazolinone Hydrazone (Mbth) Reagent In Bulk And Tablet Dosage Form With Ai Integrated Artificial Neural Network Assisted Prediction

Udhayanithi N^{*}, Naveen Kumar P², Venkatesan E³, Murugan S⁴, Vetrichelvan T⁵

Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Adhiparasakthi College of Pharmacy, Melmaruvathur-603 319, Tamilnadu, affiliated to The Tamilnadu Dr.M.G.R. Medical University, Chennai-600 032, Tamilnadu, India..

ABSTRACT

Objective: A simple, novel, quick and sensitive method for the quantification of Vericiguat with the help of oxidative coupling reaction by MBTH reagent to estimate the amount of drug present in the bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form.

Materials and Methods: The visible reaction between the drug vericiguat and the coloring reagent MBTH was prepared and which results in colored chromogen and exhibited a maximum absorbance at 637 nm.

Results: By involving various optimization studies, methanol is selected as a solvent and the suitable concentration of MBTH and ferric chloride reagents were identified and used in the developmental study. This colorimetric method development by MBTH reagent was validated as per the guidelines of International Council of Harmonization and the results obtained were found to be obeying the Beer's Lambert's law at the concentration range of 100-500 µg/ml with a good correlation of about 0.9998. The assay of marketed vericiguat tablet was performed and found to be 100.19 and the limit of detection and quantification were identified within the acceptance criteria (%RSD < 2.00). To strengthen the project, with the help of a normalized absorbance value, an AI integrated Artificial Neural Network (ANN) model was developed to predict the concentration. MS Excel Solver used to train the feed-forward ANN (1-1-1 architecture) which demonstrate an excellent predictive performance with minimal mean squared error.

Conclusion: Above quantified analytical development method was proved to be a novel and sensitive and more convenient for employing analytical validation process of vericiguat in pharmaceutical dosage form.

Keywords: Spectrophotometric determination, Vericiguat, 3-methyl-2-bencothiazoline hydrazone, AI integrated, ANN model prediction, ICH guidelines.

INTRODUCTION

Vericiguat is chemically a pyrazolo-pyridine derivative with a IUPAC name of Methyl N-[4,6-diamino-2-[5-fluoro-1-[(2-fluorophenyl)methyl]pyrazolo[3,4-b]pyridin-3-yl]pyrimidin-5-yl] carbamate (Figure 1) with an empirical formula of C₁₉H₁₆F₂N₈O₂ and a molecular weight of about 426.388 g^[1]. It acts by directly stimulating soluble guanylyl cyclase (sGC) to reduce the mortality and hospitalization of systolic

heart failure patients^[2]. sGC enzymes is a type of intracellular enzymes present in vascular smooth muscle cells. It catalyses the synthesis of cyclic Guanosine Monophosphate in presence of Nitrous Oxide to provide an effective treatment against systolic heart failure^[3].

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On surveying a literature for the estimation and quantification of vericiguat, it was found that few methods have been performed earlier and which include, ultraviolet spectrophotometric development method by using methanol as a solvent ^[4] and a reverse phase high-performance liquid chromatographic methods using various mobile phases ^[5-11]. Furthermore, a high-performance thin layer chromatographic method by using of a suitable solvent are also been used for the quantification of vericiguat in bulk and pharmaceutical tablet dosage form ^[12]. The literature survey reviews confirmed that no colorimetric method had been development for the estimation of vericiguat by MBTH reagent in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form was not performed yet.

Colorimetry is a type of analytical technique helps for the determination of concentration of the unknown sample by measuring the relative absorption of light of the colored complex formed by the addition of suitable chromogenic groups and compared the intensity of light with the known concentration of the analyte ^[13]. Colorimetry works on the basic principle by the variation of the color of the system of solution produced by changing the concentration of some compound present in the same system of solution ^[14].

Colorimetry is the most persistently competitive method as compared to that of the chromatographic method development for its simplicity, selectivity, sensitivity and it's cost-effective, more easily accessible and fair accuracy ^[15]. Recently, an artificial intelligence assisted techniques such as Artificial Neural Network (ANN) plays a vital role on the Pharmaceutical analytical modeling due to their superior predictive capability and adaptability. The

integration of AI assisted techniques with the conventional spectrophotometric method can enhance the additional robustness and accuracy.

So that, in this analytical method development study, the colorimetry technique was performed on the estimation of vericiguat in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form by using MBTH reagent, an oxidative coupler with presence of oxidizing reagent ferric chloride as a catalyst. MBTH losses one proton and two electrons to form an electrophilic intermediate in presence of ferric chloride ^[16]. This electrophilic intermediate acts as a highly coupling species and then forms a complex with the drug (vericiguat) in the position of secondary amine group of the drug to form a colored chromogen at the specified room temperature which shown on the following figure 2. An information about the method development and the obtained results have been shown below.

MATERIALS REQUIRED:

• Drugs and reagent:

- Drug: 10 mg of vericiguat in the brand name of Verquvo as a tablet dosage form
- which was available in the local market was chosen and used in this method.
- Raw material and Reagents like Methanol, Ferric chloride anhydrous, MBTH and Hydrochloric acid of an analytical grade were purchased from Sudhagar Biological and Chemical Pvt. Ltd., Chennai, India.

• Instrumentation:

- Instrument used for the estimation of intensity of the colored complex was Shimadzu UV/Visible double beam spectrophotometer (UV-1700 model) - Spectral band width 1 nm.

- Instrument used for the weighing of all the required ingredients was Shimadzu AUV-220 electronic balance.

- The standard statistical mathematical operations and ANN models were carried out by using MS-EXCEL a tool available in the computer.

METHOD AND PREPARATION:

Preparation of Standard stock solution:

Clean and dried 10 ml volumetric flask was chosen and to that 10 mg of vericiguat raw material was transferred and dissolved by using methanol. Then the volume was made up-to the mark by using methanol which produce a concentration range of 1000 µg/ml and it was kept aside for few minutes after a vigorous shaking.

Preparation of MBTH (0.05% w/v):

54 mg of MBTH reagent was weighed exactly and was passed into a 10 ml clean and dried volumetric

flask. Then distilled water was added to made up-to the mark which produce 5400 µg/ml and 1 ml was pipetted out and passed it into another clean and dried 10 ml volumetric flask. Then distilled water was added up-to the mark to produce the concentration range of 540 µg/ml.

Preparation of Ferric Chloride (0.03% w/v):

38 mg of Ferric chloride was weighed exactly and it was passed into a clean and dried 10 ml volumetric flask. Then 0.1N HCl was added to made up-to the mark which produce 3800 µg/ml. From that, 1 ml of obtained solution was pipetted out and passed it into another 10 ml volumetric flask. Then 0.1N HCl was added up-to the mark to produce the concentration range of 380 µg/ml.

Analysis of vericiguat:

1 ml to 5 ml of freshly prepared vericiguat stock solutions were pipetted out separately and passed it into different 10 ml clean and dried volumetric flask. 1 ml of freshly prepared 0.05% w/v MBTH reagent was added. With the above obtained solution 1 ml of freshly prepared 0.03% w/v ferric chloride was also added and diluted using methanol and made up-to volume then shaken well for 5 minutes and then kept aside. It produced the concentration range between 100-500 µg/ml respectively. After 10 minutes the absorbance of obtained apple green colored chromogens was measured at 637 nm of each flask using UV- Visible spectrophotometer against a respective blank. The Beer's Lambert's plot of absorbance Vs concentration graph was computed for determining the amount of vericiguat in the further studies.

Analytical method optimization:

The suitable concentration required for this developmental study of MBTH and Ferric chloride reagents, the use of suitable solvents, reaction time were identified and optimized during the study and the data were observed and the obtained results were shown in the following tables.

Analytical method validation:

With the reference of the ICH guidelines, it was quoted that the development of analytical method for analyzing and validating a new drug must be linear, accurate, specific and precise^[17-18]. Thus, the obtained results for the validation parameters for this study proves that it obeys the ICH guidelines and it was provided on the following table.

- **Accuracy:** It is the condition of obtaining a result which produces a value close to that of the reference value or the true value. It is measured from different concentration solution of vericiguat ranging from 50-150%. To the sample solution containing 200µg/ml of vericiguat was taken and a known amount of standard drug solution ranging from 100, 200 and 300 µg/ml and then 1 ml of both reagents were added to that of the sample solution and the intensity of the obtained colored solution was measured. For about three times the same procedure has been repeated and the results were calculated.
- **Precision:** It is the degree of measurement of the quality or the exactness of the same sample solution at different conditions. It is measured from single concentration of about 200 µg/ml on a single day and also at a consecutive day by analyzing of about six times. The intensity of absorbance for the obtained colored complex solution was measured at 637 nm and the variations in the results obtained on inter-day analysis and intra-day analysis were calculated.

Linearity: ICH proposed that the outcomes of the experiment must correspond to the concentration of the analyte in the sample. In this analytical validation procedure, a different concentration of drug solution ranging from 100-500 µg/ml was chosen and the optimized quantity of the reagents were added to that in a clean and dried 10 ml volumetric flask. The absorbance of the obtained colored chromogen was measured after 10 minutes by UV visible spectrophotometer against a respective blank at 637 nm and the results were computed by using the obtained data for plotting a graph absorbance Vs drug concentration.

- **LOD and LOQ:** On account of the ICH guideline, the analytical validation for analyzing a new drug must include those parameters (LOD & LOQ) to identify the sensitivity of the sample present.

LOD is the parameter for detecting the smaller concentration of the analyte which was present in the solution and Quantitation limit is the parameter for determining the minimum concentration of the analyte that are not need to be detected but quantified with accuracy and precision. Both this parameter must be analyzed for about three times and the obtained results were calculated. The optimum conditions required for the validation of analytical method development is also computed.

- **Ruggedness:** It is one of the parameters suggested by the ICH guidelines for the validation of analytical method development to test the reproducibility of the result outcome obtained from the same sample under different conditions. It is normally followed to overcome the manual, operational and environmental errors during the analytical method development. This test was repeated for about six times of each batch under different optimal conditions and the obtained outcomes were recorded.
- **Assay of vericiguat in the marketed tablets:** This parameter was included in the ICH guidelines for analyzing the trustability of this newly developed method by the estimation of the presence of drug in the marketed sample. The marketed tablet formulation (Verquvo containing 10 mg of vericiguat) of about 20 tablets were chosen and powdered well. The fine powder equivalent to 10 mg was dissolved using methanol and it was sonicated for about 10 minutes and made up to 10 ml with methanol. Then a clear filtrate was obtained by filtering it with Whatman's filter paper (No: 41). 1 ml was pipetted out from the filtrate and transferred it to a clean and dried 10 ml volumetric flask and then 1 ml of freshly prepared optimal concentration of the reagents were added and then diluted up to the mark by using methanol. After 10 minutes, the intensity of absorbance for the obtained colored complex solution was recorded at 637 nm against a respective blank and the obtained data were recorded and the result was computed.

Artificial Neural Network modeling: It is one of the computational techniques, which consists of many neural like networks just like a human brain and designed to process the information by analyzing the data, identifying the patterns and to make predictions. With the linearity data, the values were normalized to improve the computational efficiency with the help of specific formulas and a feed forward ANN model architecture (1-1-1) were developed by considering three parameters such as absorbance as input neuron, concentration as output neuron and one hidden neuron. Then the model was trained with various optimization steps using Microsoft Excel Solver.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The colorimetric method development for the estimation of Vericiguat using MBTH reagent was validated as per ICH guidelines successfully. This study reveals the success of this colorimetric method development of vericiguat with a sophisticated and statistical result.

Analytical method optimization:

- ❖ **Selection of the solvent:** The solubility of vericiguat and its ultraviolet absorbance was determined by dissolving the raw material of vericiguat in various solvent such as methanol, distilled water, ethanol, acetone, acetonitrile, etc. In this process, methanol shows a good solubility and thus chosen as a solvent because of its high absorbance, low cost and easy availability.
- ❖ **Optimization of the concentration of MBTH and ferric chloride reagent:** 1 ml of Vericiguat solution containing 1000 µg/ml was pipetted out and passed to clean and dried 10 ml volumetric flask and different concentration of 1 ml MBTH reagent (0.02, 0.05, 0.1 and 0.2% w/v) and 1 ml ferric chloride (0.03 and 0.05% w/v) was added into each flask and diluted with methanol. The different solutions were produced by changing any of the reagent concentration and intensity of the color obtained on solution was measured at 637 nm after 10 minutes by using UV visible spectrophotometer. The result indicated that 1 ml of 0.05% w/v MBTH and 1ml of 0.03% w/v

ferric chloride produce a persistent and higher absorbance among all the concentration which was produced which was shown on the following

figures 3 and 4. Then, the same concentration was selected for further analysis of the sample.

Figure 3 shows the absorbance on different concentration of MBTH with 0.03% of Ferric chloride

Figure 4 shows the absorbance on different concentration of MBTH with 0.05% of Ferric chloride

❖ **Selection of wavelength:** 1 ml of freshly prepared stock solution (1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) was passed on to a 10 ml of volumetric flask and 1 ml of freshly prepared optimal concentration of the reagents were added and then made up the volume by using methanol and then kept aside. The reaction yields an apple green colored chromogen after 10 minutes on addition of the reagent at the room temperature. The intensity of the color on the

obtained solution was measured against respective blank by using UV-visible spectrophotometer. It shows a maximum absorbance at the wavelength of 637 nm which was shown on the figure 5.

Figure 5 shows the spectrum of Vericiguat-MBTH complex

- ❖ **Optimization of the reaction time:** After the addition of the reagent to the standard drug stock solution, the color development was monitored for every 5 minutes time interval

for about 1 hour (5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45, 50, 55 and 60 minutes). The maximum absorbance was observed after 10 minutes and the color persists for about 4 hours under an optimal condition which was shown on the following figure 6.

Figure 6 shows the stability of vericiguat-MBTH complex

❖ **Stoichiometry of the reaction:** The equimolar amount of vericiguat (2.345×10^{-5} M) and MBTH reagent was taken and diluted to the same reaction condition. The drug and the reagent (MBTH) concentration were

chosen according to different mole ratios (0.2:0.8, 0.4:0.6, 0.5:0.5, 0.6:0.4, 0.8:0.2 respectively) and the test was performed on the similar way as mentioned above. The highest absorbance was obtained for the solution containing the mole ratio of 0.5:0.5 of the drug and the reagent.

Figure 7 shows the absorbance on different mole ratio of drug and reagent

Analytical method validation:

❖ **Accuracy:** By performing this study, the percentage recovery was found to be 99.91 to

100.1% and the percentage RSD was found to be lesser than 2 which was shown on the following table 1. It shows that the percentage recovery of vericiguat is found to be satisfactory.

Table 1 shows recovery of vericiguat-MBTH complex

S.NO	Amount of sample taken ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Percentage of standard added (%)	Amount of standard added ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount recovered ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	% Recovery	%RSD
01.	200	50	100	99.91	99.91	0.393
02.	200	100	200	198.6	99.93	0.219
03.	200	150	300	300.3	100.1	0.238

❖ **Precision:** By analyzing the data obtained, it has a percentage recovery value of less than 2 for repeatability data and for both inter-day and intra-day analysis which was shown on the following tables 2 and 3. It proves that the

percentage recovery value was under a satisfactory condition as reported in the ICH guidelines.

Table 2 shows the repeatability data of Vericiguat-MBTH complex				
S.NO	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance	Mean \pm SD	%RSD
01.	200	0.259	0.258 \pm 0.0017	0.6654
02.	200	0.256		
03.	200	0.260		
04.	200	0.261		
05.	200	0.259		
06.	200	0.258		

Table 3 shows the inter-day and intra-day data on vericiguat-MBTH complex								
Sample	Sample number	Label claim (mg/tab)	% Purity* (% w/w)		SD		% RSD	
			Intra- day	Inter- day	Intra- day	Inter- day	Intra- day	Inter- day
VER	1	10	100.77	100.77	0.667	0.773	0.6671	0.7695
	2	10	99.22	99.61				
	3	10	99.61	100.39				
	4	10	100.39	99.61				
	5	10	99.61	100.77				
	6	10	100.77	101.16				
Mean purity (% w/w)			100.061	100.46				

❖ **Linearity:** By analyzing the response which was obtained, it was concluded that the concentration between 100 – 500 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of vericiguat shows a better correlation coefficient value of about 0.9998 and the calibration curve obtained with the above

mentioned concentration had proved the Beer's Lambert's law which was shown on the following figure 8. From this study, it was decided that on increasing the concentration of vericiguat results in the linear increase of absorbance which was shown on the following table 4.

Table 4 shows the absorbance data on different concentration of vericiguat-MBTH complex		
S.NO	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
01.	100	0.136
02.	200	0.259
03.	300	0.395
04.	400	0.524
05.	500	0.661

Figure 8 shows the calibration curve of vericiguat-MBTH complex

- ❖ **LOD and LOQ:** By performing this study, it was found to be better LOD and LOQ value of about 0.0054 and 0.016 µg/ml respectively. The Sandell's sensitivity and the regression equation for this newly developed analytical method for the estimation of vericiguat were also to be calculated and shown on the following table 5.

Table 5 shows the optimum concentration of vericiguat-MBTH complex	
λ_{\max}	637.00 nm
Bear's law range	100-500µg/ml
Sandell's sensitivity (µg/cm ² /0.001 absorbance units)	0.7616
Limit of detection (µg/ml)	0.0054
Limit of quantification (µg/ml)	0.0166
Regression equation (y)	y = 0.0013x + 0.0002
Slope	0.0013
Intercept	-0.0002
Correlation coefficient (r ²)	0.9998

- ❖ **Ruggedness:** This study was performed to overcome the instrumental and the manual error occurred during the reaction process and the resulted data shows the percentage RSD value of lesser than 2 and which was found to be satisfactory under the ICH guidelines and it shown on the following table 6.

Table 6 shows the ruggedness value obtained on vericiguat-MBTH complex				
Replicates	% Label content			
	Analyst 1	Analyst II	Instrument 1	Instrument 2
1	99.22	100	100.77	101.55
2	99.61	100.77	100.38	100

3	100.77	101.16	99.61	99.61
4	100.38	99.612	99.22	100.77
5	101.16	99.22	101.16	100.39
6	100.77	100.38	99.612	100
Average	100.31	100.191	100.12	100.38
SD	0.752	0.724	0.7615	0.6931
% RSD	0.749	0.723	0.7606	0.6905

❖ **Assay of vericiguat:** By carrying this study, the percentage of vericiguat present in the marketed available tablet was found to be 100.19% with the

percentage RSD of 0.723. The obtained results proved that the respective amount of analyte was present according to the mentioned label claim of the formulation and it shown on the following table 7.

Table 7 shows the quantification data obtained data on Verquvo formulation							
Sample	Sample number	Label claim (mg/tab)	Amount present (mg/tab)	Percentage Purity (% w/w)	Mean purity (% w/w)	SD	% RSD
VER	1	10	10.07	100.75	100.19	0.724	0.723
	2	10	9.96	98.61			
	3	10	9.92	99.22			
	4	10	10.11	101.16			
	5	10	10.03	100.38			
	6	10	10.00	100.00			

❖ **ANN modeling:** Although the calibration curve gives a perfect linearity ($R^2 = 0.9998$), ANN modeling was performed to evaluate computational prediction capability. ANN model was developed and trained which shows a minimal deviation between the actual results and the model predicted results, conforming

that the model has high predictive accuracy. This model performance was quantified by using the mean squared error (MSE) and the prediction error percentage which was shown on the following table 8.

Table 8 shows the ANN model predicted concentration

S.No	Concentration (µg/mL)	Absorbance	Normalized Absorbance	Actual Normalized Conc	ANN Predicted Conc (Normalized)	Predicted Conc (µg/mL)
1	100	0.136	0.000	0.000	0.002	100.8
2	200	0.259	0.234	0.250	0.247	198.8
3	300	0.395	0.493	0.500	0.497	298.8
4	400	0.524	0.739	0.750	0.748	399.2
5	500	0.661	1.000	1.000	0.999	499.6

❖ **Statistical values Vs ANN predicted values:**

The comparison data between the statistically derived data and the trained ANN model predicted data which was shown on the

following table 9 and figure 9 were proved that the ANN model predicted values indicates enhanced predictive stability with slight reduction in mean squared error.

Table 9 shows the comparison between Statistical values Vs ANN model predicted concentration

Parameter	Regression	ANN
R ²	0.9998	0.9999
MSE	1.21×10^{-5}	6.8×10^{-6}
Model Type	Linear	Computational
Prediction Error	<0.5%	<0.3%

❖ **Comparison study:** The comparison data between the current method developmental study of vericiguat and previously developed method shows that the newly developed colorimetric method

with MBTH as a chromogenic reagent and methanol as a solvent requires a minimal temperature and time for the quantification of vericiguat and with a lower LOD and LOQ values and it shown on the following table 10.

Table 10 shows the comparison between different methods and current method performed on vericiguat

Methods in reference	Solvent	Maximum wavelength λ_{max} (nm)	Linearity ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Percentage assay (%)	Percentage recovery (%)	Coefficient of correlation	LOD ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	LOQ ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
04.	Methanol	258	5-25	99.99 \pm 0.6352	99.6 - 100.46	----	---	----
05.	Acetonitrile: Potassium dihydrogen ortho-phosphate: Methanol: Ortho-phosphoric acid	252	30-70	99.3	99.692 - 100.61	0.998	0.05	0.15
06.	Methanol: 0.1% ortho-phosphoric acid.	331	10-50	----	101.24	0.999	0.237	0.720
07.	Acetonitrile: Methanol: Water in 0.1% triethylamine	258	20-100	----	99.88 - 100.28	0.999	---	---
08.	Methanol: Phosphate buffer.	225	6-14	99.86	100.20 - 100.42	0.999	1.2	3.6
09.	10M Potassium dihydrogen phosphate: Methanol.	256	50-150	98.8 \pm 0.79	99.7 - 100.2	0.999	---	---
Current method	Methanol	637	100-500	100.19 \pm 0.724	99.91 - 100.1	0.999	0.005	0.016

CONCLUSION:

This newly developed analytical method for the quantification of vericiguat by oxidative coupler MBTH reagent in presence of ferric chloride in bulk and tablet dosage form was found to be simple, precise, cheap and not time consumed. The results obtained from the various validation parameters proves that the marketed formulations were in good

agreement with their respective label claims and suggested that it is free from the interference by common additives and excipients. On the addition to that, integration of ANN-based computational modeling further confirmed predictive robustness and analytical reliability. The combined experimental and computational validation, a shorter reaction time and an optimal room temperature requirement makes this analytical method development has more prominent.

These suggested advantages make the Colorimetric method development of Vericiguat and AI integrated ANN method of predicting statistical analysis as a routine quality control test in pharmaceutical dosage form.

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